

“Learning to Read Exercises”: It's Effect on Kindergarten Learners for the SY 2022-2023

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ABSTRACT: “Successful reading experiences can counter the feeling of failure;” Day and Bamford (2000). This study is conducted to know whether the workbook material “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa”, would assist in improving the reading performance of the kindergarten learners in letter name knowledge, letter sound knowledge, syllable recognition and word recognition. Researchers used the one group pre-test post-test design to determine the effect of the learning resource material to the 18 kindergarten learners. The Mean Percentage Score (MPS) were used to assess the pre and post assessment result, and Wilcoxon signed rank test to find out if there were difference in pupils’ performances in the pre-test and in the post test. The study finds out that the learners’ level of mastery in reading before the intervention is “low mastery” which means that “the learners cannot identify letter names and sounds and cannot recognize syllables and words”. The MPS of the learners increased after the intervention. The pre-assessment and post-assessment of the learners had a significant difference. The difference percentage result suggested that the workbook used in the study is effective and that the used of the workbook material is recommended to use in kindergarten to improve the learner’s performance in reading.

KEYWORD: teaching and learning resource material, parental involvement, guided reading, read-a-loud, workbook

CONTEXT AND RATIONALE

In DepEd Order No. 21 s. 2019, or the Policy Guidelines on the K to 12 Basic Education Program, it sets Flexible Learning Options (FLOs), which includes alternative delivery modes and its corresponding learning resources that are responsive to the need, context, circumstances, and diversity of learners. Hence, learning innovations are honed in all subject areas. DepEd Order no. 47, s. 2016, the Omnibus Policy on Kindergarten Education, sets the basic standards for an efficient and effective Kindergarten Program covering the following components: curriculum, instruction, assessment, learning resource and instructional materials, learning environment, and monitoring and evaluation for the standard delivery of kindergarten services. Under learning resource and instructional materials, making locally developed learning materials to aid, or enhance learning is encouraged. The advent of RA 10157 and RA 10533 is a major milestone that gives the Department of Education (DepEd) the official mandate to offer Kindergarten education to all five-year old children. This comprehensive policy ensures a standardized implementation of the Kindergarten Education Program. It entails a thorough review and analysis of the different issuances relative to kindergarten by different stakeholders with the objective of coming up with a single policy. Developmental Domains refer to the seven (7) learning areas in the Kindergarten curriculum namely: 1) Language, Literacy, and Communication (Wika, Karunungan sa Pagbasa at Pagsulat); 2) Socio-Emotional Development (Pagpapaunlad ng Sosyo-Emosyunal at Kakayahang Makipamuhay); 3) Values Development (Kagandahang Asal); 4) Physical Health and Motor Development (Kalusugang Pisikal at Pagpapaunlad sa Kakayahang Motor); 5) Aesthetic/Creative Development (Sining); 6) Mathematics (Matematika,); and 7) Understanding of the Physical and Natural Environment (Pag-unawa sa Pisikal at Natural na Kapaligiran).

“The undeniable fact remains that majority of Filipino students do not possess the ability and motivation to read. Due to the past evolving world and changing technology, it cannot be denied that sometimes reading is taken for granted” (Philippine Star 2010). The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results from PISA 2018 revealed that reading is among the areas the Philippines scored lower that is, 80% of the Filipino students did not reach the minimum level of proficiency in reading, that’s why the Department of Education launched initiative to intensify the advocacy for reading and pledging commitment to make every learner a reader at his/her grade level (Claessen et al. (2020). Reading is a complex process as it involves “sensation, perception, comprehension, application and integration”. It is the process of making and getting meaning

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from printed words and symbols. Reading is a means of communication and of information and ideas (Aracelo,1994). Moreover, reading is the foundation of academic success and life learning. Reading also plays a vital role in one’s success in school. It is one of the most important skills an individual learner needs to master. It is a pre-requisite skill of all learning areas. It serves as a gateway for every learner to learn the different subjects because when a learner has a difficulty in reading, he/she may encounter difficulties in all subject areas.

Thus, during the pandemic the proponent had innovated a learning material entitled “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa” that falls under the kindergarten developmental domains under language, literacy, and communication. The learning material passed the Division Quality Assurance by the Academic Review Board and were published in the SDO Local Repository Learning Resources, APUNAN. The said learning resource material is then of help in teaching beginning reading to kindergarten learners. As for the current school year, the proponent decided to know the impact of the said learning resource material in the reading development of the kindergarten learners.

In the current situation in our school, during this so called new normal, kindergarten learners and the primary graders as well as the intermediate level have issues on poor communication skills, and this indicates that they have difficulty in learning to read and this was proven when the PHIL-IRI group screening test was conducted which has the following results.

Table I. Sablan Central School PHIL-IRI Group Screening Test (GST) Result in Filipino (SY 2022-2023)

Grade Level	Enrolment		No. of Pupil Tested		0 - 7 score		8-13 score		14 and above score	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
3	18	11	18	11	6	4	9	5	3	2
4	29	14	29	14	3	0	9	2	17	12
5	24	13	24	13	2	0	7	2	15	11
6	25	17	25	17	14	2	6	9	4	7
TOTAL	96	55	96	55	25	6	31	18	39	32

The teachers complain that most of the young learners did not master phonemes, and they hardly read words. As this situation, the learners are struggling readers because of limited experience with books, speech and hearing problems, and poor phonemic awareness.

In Kindergarten, under the domain, Language, Literacy, and Communication on identifying sounds of letters (using the alphabet of the Mother Tongue) and naming upper case and lower-case letters (using the alphabet of the Mother Tongue) all and most of the pupils fall under the rating of beginning (B) which means that the pupils rarely demonstrate the competency. The table below shows the result of the assessment of the kindergarten learners conducted during the second quarter of the school year.

Table 2. Result of Assessment of the Kindergarten Learners conducted during the second quarter of the school year

READING (Kindergarten Progress Report Card)				
Competency	Beginning (B)	Developing (D)	Consistent (C)	TOTAL
Identifies the sounds of letters (using the alphabet Mother Tongue)	18	0	0	18
Names upper case and lower-case letters (using the alphabet of the Mother Tongue)	15	3	0	18

Through the assessment result in the report card of the pupils, the learners indeed need help in mastering the competencies in reading to improve their rating and performance as well. Through this the researchers decided to use the workbook material entitled “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa” as a learning resource material for teaching reading in school and at home. To improve the learner’s performance in reading, teachers must provide age-appropriate learning materials (Abeberese et al. (2011). Also, early literacy can be enhanced through parental involvement (Mullis, Mullis, Comille, Ritchson, & Sullender, 2002). Parents have a critical role in enhancing the literacy skills of their child through interactions. If a child is not gaining literacy skills and experiences at this stage, they have a greater risk of falling behind in reading. Thus, family involvement

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in schools leads to better attendance, higher scores on standardized tests, higher motivation to study, lower absenteeism, and improved behavior at home and at school (Dor & Rucker-Naidu, 2012)

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study aimed to determine the effect of using the learning resource material “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa” in improving the reading performance of the kindergarten learners of the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of mastery in the reading performance of the kindergarten learners as to the following before the intervention:
 - a. Letter name knowledge
 - b. Letter sound knowledge
 - c. Syllable recognition and identification
 - d. Word recognition (2-3 syllable word)
2. What is the level of mastery in the reading performance of the kindergarten learners as to the following after the intervention:
 - a. Letter name knowledge
 - b. Letter sound knowledge
 - c. Syllable recognition and identification
 - d. Word recognition (2-3 syllable word)
3. Is there a significant difference in the reading performance of the kindergarten learners before and after the intervention as to the following:
 - a. Letter name knowledge
 - b. Letter sound knowledge
 - c. Syllable recognition and identification
 - d. Word recognition (2-3 syllable word)

INNOVATION, INTERVENTION, AND STRATEGY

“Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa” is a learning resource workbook made by the proponent for kindergarten learners during the time of pandemic to help the learners master the competency in alphabet knowledge and phonological awareness.

In the study, the said learning resource material was utilized by the learners at home with their parents, and guided reading with the teacher. As interaction with more knowledgeable others such as teacher and parents who provides guidance and modelling enables the child to learn skills by engaging more interactive and challenging activities (McLeod 2024). Guided reading is based on the belief that the optimal learning for a reader occurs when they are assisted by an educator, or expert ‘other’, to read and understand a text with clear but limited guidance (Vygotsky 1978). Guided reading allows students to practise and consolidate effective reading strategies. It is also a teaching practice many teachers utilize to provide differentiated reading instruction to small groups of learners (Morgan 2023). During guided reading, students read instructional leveled texts with teacher support. Thus, the teacher guides or ‘scaffolds’ their students as they read, talk, and think their way through a text (Department of Education, 1997). In this study, the reading activities in the workbook “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa” were put in flashcards, placards, charts, and flipbooks. These served as an instructional material during the guided reading program (Kinder-A-Reader) in the study, hence one way of providing for individual differences is to use varied instructional materials, and flexible groupings. Also, children learn best when teachers employ a variety of strategies to model and demonstrate reading knowledge, strategy, and skill. In this program, the participants were grouped and had their reading schedules within the week. Children were placed in small intervention groups and worked with the teacher. The Interventions involved reading activities with the teacher, also interactive writing activities with teacher feedback and scaffolding. Participating in interactive writing will help the kindergarteners in their word reading ability also in their reading comprehension (Craig, 2003). In the workbook, the activities are combination of alphabet knowledge and phonemes. Through guided reading (Kinder-A-Reader), the pupils will be given activities in identifying letters and associate it with sounds. After the pupils master the letter names and sound, oral blending was introduced by the teacher. The activities given was blending two phonemes to make a syllable and combining the two syllables to produced words. Once the pupils are comfortable listening for individual phonemes, the teacher taught them to break up words, into component sounds. After that create a sequence of segmenting (separating a word into smaller units, such as syllables, onset-rimes, or individual phonemes) and blending activities to help students develop an understanding of the relationship

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between sounds in words. The teacher provided children with more support when first teaching a task. For example, model a sound or strategy for making the sound, and have the children use the strategy to produce the sound through a song and model and practice several examples. The children were prompt to use the strategy during guided practice, and gradually add more examples. As the students master these skills, the teacher provided less teacher-directed instruction and more practice and challenge through games and contest.

Another strategy done in the study is through parent and child reading at home (Read A-Loud with Mom). The social environment, including family members, is a considerably effective factor in the development of reading comprehension skills. Considering this effect, some researchers have drawn attention to the concept of home literacy (Burgess et al., 2002; Hiğde et al., 2020; Senechal and LeFeve, 2002). In the study, the workbook was reproduced and was given to the pupils, this served as their reading resource at home. Pupils were given reading assignment found in the workbook and they read it with their mom as to master what is taught to them during the guided reading program. The parents send videos to the teacher as one proof for their read a-loud with mom activity. It is widely accepted that parents have a significant role in their children's education and influence their learning and development (Froiland and Davison 2014; Pinquart, 2015).

Figure 1. The procedural framework in the implementation of the Reading Intervention

In this study, there are three procedural frameworks in the implementation of the reading program activities. First is the Pre-development where the researchers made and submit proposal for approval. Second is the development and validation where once the proposal is approved, now the researcher developed the instructional materials used in the program “Kinder A Reader” in executing the reading activities found in the workbook “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa”, for teaching-learning engagement in reading and the “Read A-Loud with Mom” intervention. Before the intervention, the researcher assessed the kindergarten learners using the reading assessment tool. This served as the initial data as the basis for the kindergartens’ performance. Third is the Post Development where the material is utilized by the teacher in teaching alphabet knowledge and phonological awareness to improve the reading performance of the kindergarten learners.

ACTION RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

In this study, the researchers used the one group pre-test post-test design to determine the impact of the learning resource material entitled “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa” to the reading performance of the kindergarten learners. The design is shown as:

$$O_1 \text{ ----- } X \text{ ----- } O_2$$

Where: O_1 = Pre-assessment O_2 = Post Assessment
 X = Intervention

Participants and/or Other Sources of Data and Information

This study was conducted at Sablan Central School located at Poblacion, Sablan, Benguet. The participants were the kindergarten learners for the school year 2022-2023. A total of 18 kindergarten learners participated in the study. The study is on language domain in kindergarten education under phonological awareness and alphabet knowledge. The study covered the fourth

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quarter that starts in the last week of April and ends in July 2023. The identified student underwent a reading intervention program entitled “Kinder-A-Reader” and “Read-A-Loud with Mom” across the fourth quarter. The intervention program used the workbook material “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa”. The learner’s performance was monitored from the pre-intervention to post – intervention using their assessment results.

Data Gathering Methods

To gather the data needed the researchers’ used results of the teacher made tests before and after the intervention. At the end of the second quarter, the pupils were assessed using the teacher made assessment tool in reading. The tool was content validated by five long term preschool teachers in the district. The pupils were assessed individually and orally. Their assessment scores were recorded in each category. During the intervention, the participants were monitored especially their attendance and participation in the different activities conducted. The intervention was done at the start of the third quarter until the fourth quarter of the school year. Before the school year ends, the participants had their post assessment individually and orally.

Data Analysis Plan

To answer the problems in the study, the following tools were used to treat the data statistically:

1. Mean Percentage Score (MPS)

This was the basis to answer problem number one and two and the following reference was used to interpret the data.

Percentage	Descriptive Equivalent
96 – 100%	Mastered
86 – 95%	Closely approaching mastery
66 – 85%	Moving towards mastery
35 – 65%	Average Mastery
15 – 34%	Low Mastery
5 – 14%	Very low mastery
0 – 4%	Absolutely no Mastery

2. Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test

This was the basis to answer the number three problem to know if there is a significant difference between the scores perceived before and after the intervention.

3. Pre and post observations also was used to interpret the data presented.

Ethical Issues

The researchers asked permission from the school head before implementing the study. Since the participants were minors, their parents’ consent was secured first. The personal information of the learners was kept confidential. The kindergarten learners and parents were informed about the study and its purpose, but it was done after the collection of data needed to prevent bias results.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND REFLECTION

Level of mastery in reading of the kindergarten learners before the intervention

Table 1 shows the learners’ mastery level in reading before the intervention. In the pretest, the participants’ level of mastery in letter name knowledge is “Low Mastery” with an overall MPS of 25.32% which means the learners cannot identify letter names. In letter sound knowledge, the participants’ level of mastery is “Low Mastery” with an overall MPS of 33.61% which means that the participants’ cannot identify sounds of letters. In syllable recognition, the participants’ level of mastery is “Very Low Mastery” with an MPS of 7.32% and this means that the participants cannot recognize syllables. In word recognition, the participants’ level of mastery is “Absolutely No Mastery” which means that the learners cannot recognize words.

In the table, it shows that not all the learners have low mastery, but some learners can identify letter names, and some can recognize letter sounds, syllables, and words but still needs more intervention to improve their reading performance.

Based on the data presented it could be gleaned from the tables that the learners did not perform well in their pre-assessment and it is crucial to give an intervention to enhance the performance of participants in reading. Getting a low performance in pre-assessment have many factors as observed by the teacher and according to some parent. Based on the parent-teacher conferences conducted, the reasons of low performance of their children are the following: there are no available learning materials at home for them to follow-up their children’s lesson; and some are not motivated to learn because most of their children spend a lot of time in social media, and online games, also some were lazy to do simple

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reading activities at home thus they have low performance. Based on this observation from the parents, it shows that the learners are not motivated to learn.

The result implies that teachers and parents have a great impact in the performance of the learners in reading thus teachers should modify and plan the guiding principles in teaching reading and writing. The teachers then should guide or scaffolds their pupils as they read, talk, and think their way through a text because learners learn best when teachers employ variety of strategies to model and demonstrate reading knowledge, strategy, and skill. Parent involvement also contributes to children’s overall educational achievement as well as their literacy development. Home literacy is critical in helping children who read below grade level. Parents have a great impact in motivating their children to learn. Learning resources/materials at home also can motivate the child to learn to read with the help of their loved ones. The general picture derived from the research supports the assertion that family involvement leads to better attendance, higher scores, higher motivation to study, lower absenteeism, and improved behaviour at home and school (Dor & Rucker-Naidu, 2012).

The study corroborates with Stutzel (2019), who implied that parental involvement in children’s learning leads to better educational outcomes (Berthelsen & Walker, 2008). Also, according to Brown (2007), motivation is something that can be like self-esteem, something global, situational or task oriented. Reading motivation isn’t a simple matter of desire to read. Motivation is an essential factor in learning because it has an influence in the learners’ success. Since motivation and parental involvement is an essential factor in beginning reading, teachers should implement strategies that boost the interest of the learners and keep them motivated to read. Also, teachers should know the different learning styles of the learners to know what approaches, activities, and methods to use to cater the needs of the learners. The parents also need to bond with their children for them to feel loved by them to get a positive result.

Table 1: MPS of Pre-assessment

Learner	Letter Name Knowledge (52 pts)			Letter Sound Knowledge (20 pts)			Syllable Recognition (22 pts)			Word Recognition (10 pts)		
	Score	MPS	Pre-test description	Score	MPS	Pre-test description	Score	MPS	Pre-test description	Score	MPS	Pre-test description
#1	30	57.69	Average Mastery	10	50.00	Average Mastery	5	22.73	Low Mastery	2	20.00	Low Mastery
#2	1	1.92	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#3	17	32.69	Low Mastery	15	75.00	Moving Towards Mastery	3	13.64	Very Low Mastery	1	10.00	Low Mastery
#4	19	36.54	Average Mastery	11	55.00	Average Mastery	2	9.09	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Low Mastery
#5	2	3.85	Absolutely No Mastery	1	5.00	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Low Mastery
#6	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	1	5.00	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Low Mastery
#7	30	57.69	Average Mastery	10	50.00	Average Mastery	2	9.09	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Low Mastery
#8	10	19.23	Low Mastery	6	30.00	Low Mastery	1	4.55	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Low Mastery
#9	40	76.92	Moving Towards Mastery	15	75.00	Moving Towards Mastery	6	27.27	Low Mastery	5	50.00	Average Mastery
#10	25	48.08	Average Mastery	10	50.00	Average Mastery	3	13.64	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#11	25	48.08	Average Mastery	11	55.00	Average Mastery	2	9.09	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#12	10	19.23	Low Mastery	8	40.00	Average Mastery	1	4.55	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#13	15	28.85	Low Mastery	12	60.00	Average Mastery	3	13.64	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#14	5	9.62	Very Low Mastery	4	20.00	Very Low Mastery	1	4.55	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#15	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	2	10.00	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#16	3	5.77	Very Low Mastery	1	5.00	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#17	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	1	5.00	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#18	5	9.62	Very Low Mastery	3	15.00	Very Low Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
MPS	25.3205	Low Mastery	MPS	33.61	Low Mastery	MPS	7.32	Very Low Mastery	MPS	4.44	Absolutely No Mastery	

Legend: Absolutely No Mastery- 0 to 4%; Very Low Mastery- 5 to 15%; Low Mastery- 16 to 34%; Average Mastery- 35 to 65%; Moving Towards Mastery - 66 to 85%; Closely Approximating Mastery- Mastered - 96-100%

Level of Mastery of the participants in reading after the intervention.

Table 2 shows the mastery level of the participants in reading after using the workbook “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa”. The level of mastery of the participants in letter name knowledge is “Moving Towards Mastery” with an MPS of 80.77% which is far better than the pre-assessment result which means that after the intervention the learners improved their performance but still some cannot identify letters as shown in the table. In letter sound knowledge, the participants’ level of mastery is “Closely Approximating Mastery” with an MPS of 94.17% and is far better than the pre-assessment result which means that there is an improvement of the learners’ reading performance after the intervention. In the table it shows that the participants can identify letter sounds than identifying letter names. In syllable recognition, the participants level of mastery is “Average Mastery” with an MPS of 63.38% which means that after the intervention the participants can identify syllables but some of the learners still needs more intervention. In word recognition, the participants level of mastery is “Average Mastery” with an MPS of

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59.44% which means that the participants can identify words after the intervention which is far better than without the intervention done.

The overall results of the post assessment shows that the performance of the respondents is far better after the intervention. Thus, the use of the workbook reading material “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa”, is effective. The results implies that when learners are directly exposed to the material with the help of the teacher and parent improves their performance in reading. The result is also credited to the cooperation and participation of the learners and support from the learners’ parents. The use of guided reading intervention also contributed to the positive result of the post assessment. The use of the workbook material with varied strategies in teaching reading that caters with the different learning style of the pupils is effective. Workbooks highly impact student learning outcomes. They are one of the most effective learning sources besides classroom teaching. They make the curriculum easy to understand through interactive exercises and activities. However, workbooks are effective only if they are properly utilized (Bulsjeta, 2013). Therefore, teachers need interventions to teach the reading activities in their workbook. The intensity of an intervention can be determined by many characteristics, but three are common: group size, duration of the intervention, and quality of the personnel delivering the intervention, and the associated amount of training they receive (Gersten et al., 2008). The content of the intervention should be in lined with the learning resource material used in the study that covers the four of the five areas of literacy outlined in the National Reading Panel (Ehri et al., 2001) and the National Literacy Panel for Language Minority Students (August & Shanahan, 2006): phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension. Teachers use the common instructional procedures included modelling, scaffolding, and corrective feedback in the interventions done for a positive result, these features included using visuals and gestures, building background knowledge or activating prior knowledge, clarifying meanings of words and others (Denton et al., 2004).

The study corroborates the study of Bulsjeta (2013) which found out that the purpose and role of teaching and learning resources doesn't only consist of making the educational process more attractive and interesting, but also of encouraging active learning, the development of different skills and the adoption of desirable values and attitudes in students. To achieve the goals, it is extremely important to clearly define the conditions and methods of utilising teaching and learning resources in the teaching and learning process. Using learning resources especially workbooks in reading inside the classroom and at home promotes independent thinking in children. Including various types of activities helps children think on their own about how to apply the concepts learned in the class. With the use of workbooks, the parent plays a more active part. They can track the progress and skill development of their child even at home. This also helps teachers ensure the child doesn't lag in their studies. Using a workbook will keep the learners engaged during breaks or vacations, they stay in touch with their studies thus the participants improved in their performance.

On the other hand, as it was shown in the table that after the intervention some of the pupils still could not identify letter names, but they can identify the sounds of letters. Also, the same pupils on the list had absolutely no mastery in syllable and word recognition. This implies that some of the learners didn't improve in their performance while using the workbook or intervention such as guided reading and reading a-loud with mom. As an observation, these pupils were not attending the guided reading intervention by the teacher and some come as they like. Their parents also don't have time to read with their child because of work and some had family problems that's why the participants were not engaged with the material and there is no parental involvement during the intervention. According to Beaty (2013) children can emerge into reading with appropriate books and support from an adult and the conventional process of learning to read occurs when teachers take charge and have children follow their directions.

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Table 2. MPS of the Post assessment

Learner	Letter Name Knowledge (52 pts)			Letter Sound Knowledge (20 pts)			Syllable Recognition (22 pts)			Word Recognition (10 pts)		
	Score	MPS	Pre-test description	Score	MPS	Pre-test description	Score	MPS	description	Score	MPS	Pre-test description
#1	52	100.00	Mastered	20	100.00	Mastered	22	100.00	Mastered	10	100.00	Mastered
#2	28	53.85	Absolutely No Mastery	9	45.00	Average Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#3	52	100.00	Mastered	20	100.00	Mastered	22	100.00	Mastered	10	100.00	Mastered
#4	52	100.00	Mastered	20	100.00	Mastered	22	100.00	Mastered	10	100.00	Mastered
#5	14	26.92	Absolutely No Mastery	20	100.00	Mastered	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Low Mastery
#6	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	20	100.00	Mastered	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#7	52	100.00	Mastered	20	100.00	Mastered	22	100.00	Mastered	10	100.00	Mastered
#8	52	100.00	Mastered	20	100.00	Mastered	22	100.00	Mastered	10	100.00	Mastered
#9	52	100.00	Mastered	20	100.00	Mastered	22	100.00	Mastered	10	100.00	Mastered
#10	52	100.00	Mastered	20	100.00	Mastered	22	100.00	Mastered	2	20.00	Low Mastery
#11	52	100.00	Mastered	20	100.00	Mastered	22	100.00	Mastered	10	100.00	Mastered
#12	52	100.00	Mastered	20	100.00	Mastered	22	100.00	Mastered	10	100.00	Mastered
#13	52	100.00	Mastered	20	100.00	Mastered	22	100.00	Mastered	10	100.00	Mastered
#14	52	100.00	Mastered	20	100.00	Mastered	16	72.73	Moving Towards Mastery	8	80.00	Moving Towards Mastery
#15	40	76.92	Moving Towards Mastery	20	100.00	Mastered	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#16	49	94.23	Closely Approximating Mastery	17	85.00	Moving Towards Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery	0	0.00	Absolutely No Mastery
#17	13	25.00	Low Mastery	13	65.00	Average Mastery	0	0.00	Mastery	0	0.00	Mastery
#18	40	76.92	Moving Towards Mastery	20	100.00	Mastered	15	68.18	Moving Towards Mastery	7	70.00	Moving Towards Mastery
MPS	80.769		Moving Towards Mastery	MPS	94.17	Closely Approximating Mastery	MPS	63.38	Average Mastery	MPS	59.44	Average Mastery

Legend: Absolutely No Mastery - 0 to 4%; Very Low Mastery - 5 to 15%; Low Mastery - 16 to 34%; Average Mastery - 35 to 65%; Moving Towards Mastery - 66 to 85%; Closely Approximating Mastery 86 - 95%; Mastered - 96-100%

Differences in the reading performance of the kindergarten learners before and after the intervention.

Table 3a shows the comparison of the pre and post assessment result of the respondents in letter name knowledge. In letter name knowledge, the value of W is 0. The critical value of W at N = 17 (p < .05) is 34. The test statistics (W) is less than and not equal to the tests critical value at 0.05 which is 34, therefore there is a significant difference between the scores perceived by the participants before and after the intervention.

Table 3a: Comparison of the pre-assessment and post assessment result of the respondents using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test on letter sound knowledge.

A. Letter Name Knowledge						
Pupils	Pre-Assessment Scores	Post-Assessment Scores	signed	Abs	RANK	Sign R
#1	30	52	-1	22	4.5	-4.5
#2	1	28	-1	27	7	-7
#3	17	52	-1	35	10.5	-10.5
#4	19	52	-1	33	9	-9
#5	2	14	-1	12	1.5	-1.5
#6	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#7	30	52	-1	22	4.5	-4.5
#8	10	52	-1	42	14.5	-14.5
#9	40	52	-1	12	1.5	-1.5
#10	25	52	-1	27	7	-7
#11	25	52	-1	27	7	-7
#12	10	52	-1	42	14.5	-14.5
#13	15	52	-1	37	12	-12
#14	5	52	-1	47	17	-17
#15	0	40	-1	40	13	-13
#16	3	49	-1	46	16	-16
#17	0	13	-1	13	3	-3

Result details: W=0, N=17, Mean difference=-15.71, sum of pos rank=0, sum of neg ranks = 153

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Table 3b shows the comparison of the pre and post assessment result of the respondents in letter sound knowledge. In letter sound knowledge, the value of W is 0. The critical value for W at N = 18 ($p < .05$) which is 40. The result of the tests at W is zero (0) and it is less than and not equal to the tests critical value ($p < .05$) which is 40. The result of the pre-assessment and post assessment in letter sound knowledge is significant at $p < .05$.

Table 3b: Comparison of the pre-assessment and post assessment result of the respondents using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test on letter sound knowledge.

B. Letter Sound Knowledge

Pupils	Pre-Assessment Scores	Post-Assessment Scores	sign	Abs	R	Signed R
#1	10	20	-1	10	8	-8
#2	0	9	-1	9	5	-5
#3	15	20	-1	5	1.5	-1.5
#4	11	20	-1	9	5	-5
#5	1	20	-1	19	17.5	-17.5
#6	1	20	-1	19	17.5	-17.5
#7	10	20	-1	10	8	-8
#8	6	20	-1	14	12	-12
#9	15	20	-1	5	1.5	-1.5
#10	10	20	-1	10	8	-8
#11	11	20	-1	9	5	-5
#12	8	20	-1	12	10.5	-10.5
#13	12	20	-1	8	3	-3
#14	4	20	-1	16	13.5	-13.5
#15	2	20	-1	18	16	-16
#16	1	17	-1	16	13.5	-13.5
#17	1	13	-1	12	10.5	-10.5
#18	3	20	-1	17	15	-15

Result details: W-value: 0, Mean Difference: -2.28, Sum of pos. ranks: 0, Sum of neg. ranks: 171, Sample Size (N): 18

Table 3c shows the comparison of the pre and post assessment result of the respondents in syllable recognition. In syllable recognition, the value of W is also 0 and its critical value at N=12 ($p, .05$) is 13. The result of the tests at W is zero (0) and it is less than and not equal to the critical value ($p < .05$) which is 13, therefore there is a significant difference of scores obtained by the respondents before and after the intervention in syllable recognition

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Table 3c. Comparison of the pre-assessment and post assessment result of the respondents using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test on letter sound knowledge.

C. Syllable Recognition

Pupils	Pre-Assessment Scores	Post-Assessment Scores	sign	Abs	R	Signed R
#1	5	20	-1	17	4	-4
#2	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#3	3	22	-1	19	6	-6
#4	2	22	-1	20	9	-9
#5	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#6	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#7	2	22	-1	20	9	-9
#8	1	22	-1	21	11.5	-11.5
#9	6	22	-1	16	3	-3
#10	3	22	-1	19	6	-6
#11	2	22	-1	20	9	-9
#12	1	22	-1	21	11.5	-11.5
#13	3	22	-1	19	6	-6
#14	1	16	-1	15	1.5	-1.5
#15	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#16	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#17	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#18	0	15	-1	15	1.5	-1.5

Result details: W-value: 0, Mean Difference: 2.42, Sum of pos. ranks: 0, Sum of neg. ranks: 78, Sample Size (N): 18

Table 3d shows the comparison of the pre and post assessment result of the respondents in word recognition. In word recognition, the value of W is zero (0) and it is less than and not equal to the tests critical value ($p < .05$) which is 40 so there is a significant difference between the scores perceived before and after the intervention.

Table 3d Comparison of the pre-assessment and post assessment result of the respondents using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test on letter word recognition.

D. Word Recognition

Pupils	Pre-Assessment Scores	Post-Assessment Scores	sign	Abs	R	Signed R
#1	2	10	-1	8	4.5	-4.5
#2	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#3	1	10	-1	9	6	-6
#4	0	10	-1	10	9.5	-9.5
#5	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#6	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#7	0	10	-1	10	9.5	-9.5
#8	0	10	-1	10	9.5	-9.5
#9	5	10	-1	5	2	-2
#10	0	2	-1	2	1	-1
#11	0	10	-1	10	9.5	-9.5
#12	0	10	-1	10	9.5	-9.5
#13	0	10	-1	10	9.5	-9.5
#14	0	8	-1	8	4.5	-4.5
#15	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#16	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#17	0	0	n/a	0	n/a	n/a
#18	0	7	-1	7	3	-3

Result details: W-value: 0, Mean Difference: 0.67, Sum of pos. ranks: 0, Sum of neg. ranks: 78, Sample Size (N): 12

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As stated in all the tables, all the four categories in the study before and after the intervention the scores of the respondents in the pre and post assessment is statistically significant, and the scores of the respondents after the intervention increased. The implication of the results of the assessment is that the performance of the pupils in reading after the intervention is better than when there is no intervention done. After the intervention, most of the learners mastered letter names and sounds and some can read syllables and words. This means that the use of the workbook, “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa”, is effective in improving the reading performance of the kindergarten learners with the proper guidance of the teacher employing the different strategies, methods, and approaches in utilising the learning resource material. Also, the strategy done which involves the parent of the respondents in reading at home is effective. Thus, the researchers had reached the conclusion that the unprecedented improvement in reading performance of the pupils underscored the effectiveness of the workbook “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa”.

The study corroborates with the study of Astri & Wahab (2018) who found out that learning resource materials is effective in improving students’ reading. However, students are individuals with individual needs, interests, and methods of processing information (Deporter & Hernacki, 2004) so we need to know the different learning style of the learners and consider it in making our own learning resource material. There are also several variables in teaching reading that we need to consider such as motivation, learning style, personality, metacognitive and talent (Griffiths, 2008). Based on these variables, the teacher must make a reference in presenting the activities found in the workbook to the pupils so that knowledge, skills, and attitudes can be well received. Thus, the use of the workbook material and the intervention to be implemented must be in accordance with the skills that will be taught to the pupils. According to Moghaddas (2013), contextualization is a significant learning process that takes place by linking ideas and principles from other disciplines. When a teacher organizes, designs, and creates instructional learning activities, context should be considered. On the other hand, teachers must be adaptable and imaginative while utilizing localization and contextualization in the classroom. This agrees with the study because the workbook used was contextualized and localized by the teacher for kindergarten learners.

REFLECTION

Considering the findings of the study, teachers and parents should collaborate in the teaching learning process especially in beginning reading (Beaty 2013). Teachers need to develop learning materials that is in lined with the level of the learners with interactive and engaging activities to keep the learners motivated to learn. Parental involvement is also a factor in improving the child’s performance in reading. Teachers also should consider the different learning styles of the pupils and include it in developing materials and making interventions.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The mastery level of the participants before the intervention in letter recognition is “low mastery” and improved to “moving towards mastery” in the post assessment. In letter sound recognition, the mastery level of the participants is “low mastery” and improved to “closely approximating mastery in the post assessment. The mastery level of the participants in syllable recognition before the intervention is “very low mastery” and improved to “average mastery” after the intervention. The mastery level of the participants in word recognition before the intervention is also “very low mastery” and improved to “average mastery” after the intervention. These results show that there is a significant difference in the pre assessment and post assessment result of the kindergarten learners before and after the intervention.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Most of the participants cannot identify letter names and sounds and cannot recognize syllables and words before the intervention. Although some have acquired basic knowledge and skills in identifying letter names and sounds and can recognize syllables and words but still needs more intervention.
2. Most of the participants have mastered letter names and sounds, and they can recognize syllables and words after the intervention, but some still cannot reach the average mastery level.
3. The use of the workbook “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa” can help to enhance the reading performance of the kindergarten learners with the strategy guided reading and parental involvement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are offered:

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1. Learners need to acquire the skills in phonemic awareness. It is suggested that teachers use learning materials with contextualize activities in phonemes to improve the kindergarten learner’s performance.
2. Since the use of the workbook “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa” improved the performance of the learners, it is then suggested to continue utilizing the material.
3. While the current study has demonstrated the effectiveness of the material “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa”, it is recommended to conduct further research with a wider range of participants and implement the intervention done to confirm and extend these findings.

ACTION PLAN

The researchers had disseminated the result of this study through LAC, also it was disseminated during the general parent teacher’s community association meeting. The researcher will propose an In-service Training (InSeT) Program to teachers within the school, so that easy relay of information will be disseminated with ease. The purpose of this is to give light to teachers who deal with struggling pupils in reading especially in the key stage 1 learners. Also to share the interventions done in the study that will in the improvement of reading performance of the learners. Once the completion report was accepted, information dissemination will be conducted to the kindergarten teachers in Sablan district especially those who are utilizing the workbook material “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa” through district meeting with proper protocol. As the teacher proponent, continuous utilization of the workbook material is encouraged together with the reading intervention used in this study. Lastly, to circulate research result to any platform available.

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Jovelyn C. Utang

Luz M. Merino

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FINANCIAL REPORT

A. Supplies and Materials							
Activity	Item	Unit	Quantity	Estimated Cost	Total Estimated Cost	Actual Cost	Total Cost
Implementation of the study and preparation of research papers, instructional materials/ worksheets, and other documents	A4 folder with fastener	pc	20	15	300.00	17.00	340.00
	Canon Printer ink black	Bottle	3	450	1350	475.00	1,425.00
	Canon Printer ink magenta	Bottle	3	420	1260	435.00	1,305.00
	Canon Printer ink cyan	Bottle	3	420	1260	435.00	1,305.00
	Canon Printer ink yellow	Bottle	3	420	1260	435.00	1,305.00
	A4 bond paper	ream	10	250	2500	275.00	2,750.00
	Colored paper	ream	1	250	250	280.00	280.00
	Pentel pen	pc	3	60	180	66.00	198
	glue	pc	2	50	100	60.00	120
	Laminating film	ream	1	300	300	375.00	375.00
	Ring clip	box	1	100	100	120.00	120.00
B. Reproduction, Printing, and Binding cost							
Research reading assessment tool	Answer sheets	pc	36	1	36	2.00	72.00
Learning resource material binding	workbook	pc	18	50	1260	60.00	1,080.00

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C. Communication Expenses								
During the implementation and preparation of research papers and other documents	Cell phone load card	pc	3	290	870	300.00	900.00	
	Internet load	e-load	5	99	495	105.00	525.00	
D. Other Expenses								
Snack and Food for the final coaching and deliberation of the research paper	Snack and food	pax	6	120	720	150.00	1,350.00	
TOTAL					12,241.00		13,450.00	

APPENDICES

Written Letter of Consent

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
Cordillera Administrative Region
SCHOOLS DIVISION OF BENGUET
 Sablan District
Sablan Central School
 Poblacion, Sablan, Benguet

CONSENT FORM

PART I: INFORMATION SHEET

- **Title of Research:** Gamified Reading Activities: "It's Effect to Kindergarten Learners for the SY 2022-2023"
- **Name of Proponent/s:** JOVELYN C. UTANG, T3 and LUZ M. MERINO, SP-II
- **Aims of the Study:**
 The study aims to help the pupils in mastering the competencies in alphabet knowledge and phonological awareness through the use of gamified reading activities based on the material "Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa".
- **Participant Selection:**
 In this study, the respondents will be the kindergarten learners for the school year 2022-2023 for the material is intended for kindergarten learners. The respondents can choose to participate or not for this is a voluntary participation.

PART II: CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT

1. I confirm that I have fully understood the information given to me by the researcher/s for the above study and I have had the opportunity to ask questions to the researcher/s.
2. I understand that the participation of my child/ward in this study is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without prejudice.
3. I agree that my child/ward will take part in the above study.
4. I understand that while information gained during the study may be published, my child/ward will not be identified, and his/her personal results will remain confidential.

Name of Parent/Guardians

Date

Signature

Lina B. Lorena
DANZIL R. PASIAN

9-15-22
9/15/22

[Signature]
[Signature]

“Learning to Read Exercises”: It's Effect on Kindergarten Learners for the SY 2022-2023

Latter of Permission to conduct study

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
Cordillera Administrative Region
SCHOOLS DIVISION OF BENGUET
Sablan District
Sablan Central School

September 5, 2022

ADORACION T. SIMON, PhD

School Principal II
School Head
Sablan Central School

Madam:

May we request permission to conduct research entitled “Mga Pagsasanay sa Pagkatutong Bumasa”: Its Effect to Kindergarten Learners for the SY 2022-2023. The objective of this action research is to know the effectiveness of the learning resource material on the reading performance of kindergarten learners in our school for this school year.

We look forward with gratitude for your favorable consideration on this earnest request.

Very Truly yours,

JOVELYN C. UTANG

Kindergarten Adviser/Researcher

LUZ M. MERINO, EdD

School Principal II/Researcher

Approved:

ADORACION T. SIMON, PhD

SP-II/ School Head

Assessment Tool

LM's use in the research (workbook)

(Attached soft bound)

Name: _____ Date: _____

A. Letter Recognition

Percent Correct: _____

Point to the letter, say the letter name.

h	o	X	t	m	q	M	f	Z
z	i	A	Q	J	G	E	l	u
B	j	p	s	x	K	n	k	W
e	C	c	d	U	R	V	L	s
v	l	o	t	F	g	y	P	
y	N	w	D	H	a	b	r	

B. Letter Sounds

Percent Correct: _____

Point to the letter, say the sound.

a	m	t	l	s	r	v	d	i	g
p	h	n	o	b	f	u	z	k	r

C. Syllable Recognition

Point to the syllable, sound out syllables, read syllables.

ka ma	ma ta	ga bi	ra sa	si ra
ma na	da la	pe ra	pu no	me sa

D. Word Recognition

Percent Correct: _____

Point to the word, read word.

Ang aso	
Si Ema ay may aso.	
Mataba ang baka.	
Sasama si Ema sa	
Masaya si Eva.	

Dalaga ang babae.	
Malaki ang bola.	
Palaka si Kaka.	
Si Rosa ay mabait.	
Malaki ang kama.	